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THE ORETICAL ASSESSMENT OF KARAKOL FUR DEVELOPMENT AND ITS UNIQUENESS

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Annotation: *This article provides – the main product of karakul sheep is Karakol skin, the origin of the word “Karakol”, Karakol can be of different colors, Karakol lamp skins are divided by type, color, and defect category. According to the age of the animal and the characteristics of the hair cover, it refers to varieties according to the condition of the skin.*

Keywords: *Karakol sheeps, karakul skin, fur, black leather, uniqueness, shape of culs, silky hairs, breed, blackbuck skin, astrakhan, swakara.*

Cattle breeding is one of the livestock breeding industries that develop in desert regions. Karakol sheep are bred in more than 40 countries around the world, including the Republic of South Africa, Namibia, Argentina, Iran, Germany, Austria, Moldova, Romania, Russia, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan It is grown in Estonia and other republics.

The main product of Karakol sheep is Karakol skin. The uniqueness and shape of the curls, their diversity, the brightness and silky softness of the hair coat, the elegance of their hairs have made black leather skins popular. Karakol furs are among the products in high demand among the population [1]. Therefore, great attention is paid to the quality of Karakol products.

Karakol - 1-3 days after the birth of lambs of the Karakol breed, the wool is distinguished by a thick, elastic, silky wool cover, which forms curls of various shapes and sizes.

The word "Karakul" entered the Russian language in the middle of the 19th century. It was recorded for the first time in Ilya Brezin's encyclopedic dictionary [2] (1878) with the hyphenated spelling Kara-kul.

This term is lexically-semantically derived from the Uzbek toponym Kara-kul, where a special breed of sheep with black curly wool was bred.

The name of the city, in turn, originates from the nearby lake of the same name [3], which derives its name from the Turkic words kara - "black" and kul - "lake".

In the languages of Western Europe, blackberry is "Astrakhan" (English astrakhan [4], French astrakan or astracan [5], Spanish astracán [4], etc.) is named after the Russian city of Astrakhan, the main trading center that was once engaged in the trade of black sheep.

Originally, only the natural skins of Karakol lambs bred in Central Asia were called Karakol. However, in the 1960s, faux fur with very short, silky hairs that form a raised moiré pattern on the surface and adhere tightly to the base fabric was also called black fur. The word "Karakol" itself comes from Turkic languages and literally means "black lake", although Karakol can be of different colors (grey, gray) [16].

Karakol is one of the most popular types of fur in the world market. Uzbek Karakol sheep are descendants of all types of Karakol sheep. This breed of sheep was very popular among the peoples of Central Asia due to its simplicity and perfect adaptation to semi-desert conditions. In the Middle

Ages, trade caravans carried black pelts from Bukhara and Khorezm along the entire Great Silk Road to the Mediterranean Sea, from where they spread throughout Europe. The history of Karakol goes back thousands of years, because sheep breeding is one of the oldest occupations of mankind. Perfectly adapted to the semi-desert climate, [17] Karakol sheep are widespread in the Middle East and North Africa, including Namibia. Local specialization was aimed at breeding sheep with long and parallel strands, dense, short and clearly curled [18].

Karakol sheep are the first species of domestic animals raised for their unique fur. This breed of sheep was very popular among the people of Central Asia due to its simplicity and perfect adaptation to semi-desert conditions. According to assumptions, the history of Karakol sheep began in the VIII century in the Khorezm Khanate in the Bukhara region. Uzbek Karakol sheep are descendants of modern sheep [6].

In the 10th century, the Arab geographer and traveler Ibn Haukal gave written testimony about the trade of blackbuck skins. In the 13th century, the famous traveler Marco Polo enthusiastically described the Karakol motifs in his writings about Central Asia. In the 15th century, the famous Russian writer and tourist from Tver Afanasy Nikitin brought black leather from Bukhara to Russia. From the Middle Ages to the 16th century, Bukhara merchants carried luxurious soft black leather on camels along the Great Silk Road from Asia to the Mediterranean Sea, and from there it spread to all of Europe. Merchants of the Bukhara Emirate sold blackberries and blackberries in the markets of Germany, Italy, Greece, and Scandinavian countries [19].

Karakol lamb skins are divided by type, color and defect category. According to the age of the animal and the characteristics of the hair cover, it refers to varieties according to the condition of the skin [7]

In the 17th and 18th centuries, merchants from Bukhara and Khiva supplied Russia with excellent black leather. In the markets of Moscow, Tobolsk and Tver, in Nizhny Novgorod and Irbit, merchants offered lamb skins. In the 19th century, black fur took a special place at international fur auctions in New York, Leipzig, London and was very popular among buyers [6]. At the beginning of the 20th century, until 1900, the Central Asian khanates, and later Russia, were the monopolists in the supply of karakol in the world market. Great interest in Karakol served to breed Karakol sheep at a scientific level in Europe - German and Austrian agricultural institutes. In 1907, a batch of Karakol sheep was brought from Bukhara to Austria, six heads were taken to the southwestern part of the African continent.

Thus, the history of the development of a completely new direction in cattle breeding – the Namibian cattle or "swakara" began. Swakara is an abbreviation of South –West Africa's popular brand Karakul . With the establishment of Soviet power in Uzbekistan in 1917, the number of sheep decreased significantly. Not only people, but also animals suffered in the struggle between the Beklar and the "new government". The herds were partially exterminated, 70,000 head of animals were stolen to Iran, about 400,000 sheep were sent by the landowners to the territory of Afghanistan, which was the beginning of the Afghan Karakole. In each of these countries, cattle breeding took its own path, which led to the creation of three similar, but not identical, types of cattle: Uzbek, Afghan and South African. Karakoli.

In the 1920s, production volume in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan was estimated at 1013-1800 thousand pieces per year [8]. 1058.2 thousand units in Uzbekistan in 2016 blackberry is cultivated [9]. It was also produced in Kazakhstan [10].

Kapron fibers are also used as an artificial material replacing Karakol [11-12]. There are four main markets for fur trade in the world market: Europe, North America, Russia and Asia. Traditionally, the bulk of fur clothing and fur semifinished products and raw materials are supplied to the Russian market [13] from Greece, Turkey, Italy, Denmark, Finland, Hungary and the Czech Republic.

Sheep were also brought from Uzbekistan to Iran for breeding. Karakol sheep are purebred in this country, but in most cases they are also crossbred with local sheep. In particular, black and blue black sheep are bred in the territory of Iran. Iran's blue black leathers have unique patterns and hues, as well as expensive brown and silver leathers. The wool part of these skins is soft, the curls are a little loose, open type; consists of short pencil, bean, ring and permed curls.

The Karakol sheep breed is a coarse-wool tailed sheep bred for its fur [14]. This sheep breed was created a few hundred years ago in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan (Karakol District, Bukhara Region) as a result of long-term selection and breeding of Jaidari sheep by the method of folk selection. The Karakol sheep breed is bred in more than 50 countries (about 15 million heads) on all continents of the world (except Australia). Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Iran, and the Republic of South Africa are the countries where the largest number of Karakol sheep breeds are grown.

In Uzbekistan, there were entrepreneurs who had their own position in the field of blackberry and blackberry trade. For example, the achievements of Pirnafasov Chorikulboy (1847 - 1934) for the breeding of Bukhara sheep are of particular importance. At the same time, the participation of the emir of Bukhara, Syed Olim Khan, in the trade of black sheep is mentioned in the sources. It is mentioned in the sources that Fayzulla Khojaev's father, son of Ubaidullohoja Kasimhoja (1858-1912), earned 1 million gold soums from cattle trade. In the cities of Russia and Europe, he had special stores selling blackberry and blackberry [15].

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